

Research into a standalone photovoltaic-wind hybrid microgrid system is something that really interests me, and I'm constantly looking for solutions.

During high school, scientific methodology always fascinated me. When I was in the 10th grade, our physics teacher told us about the photovoltaic system. He didn't tell us about its details, how it works, or not. But I was very curious to know about it.

I learned it in detail when I participated in a project on solar energy systems in 11th grade. That time I read a lot of books and searched the internet, and I was really shocked to learn how integrating digital technology with electrical networks could drastically enhance energy distribution and utilization.

We can see that the supply of conventional power sources is dwindling daily, and technological advancements are driving up demand for electricity. The main sources of energy consumed are oil, gas, and coal. The rate of use of fossil fuels is concerning because their supply is running out faster than expected, and they run out of stock in a matter of years. In addition, traditional sources have many disadvantages, such as the fact that they typically affect the environment.

In this situation, we must think of alternatives. Alternatives like geothermal energy, solar energy, wind energy, etc. are being used in a lot of places, but a photovoltaic system is the best choice, I think. There are lots of reasons why we think about photovoltaic systems. Among all the alternatives, photovoltaic arrays are frequently used as solar energy is abundant in nature. Besides, photovoltaic arrays are noiseless and have no moving parts. Among other renewable energy sources, wind and tidal have significant contributions. To utilize such a distributed energy system, special arrangements are needed. Microgrids combine such distributed resources to optimize energy resources and increase energy efficiency.

Microgrids provide a way to continue supplying dependable electricity during times when renewable energy sources are unavailable while also reducing carbon emissions. Since microgrids don't have massive assets, miles of above-ground cables, or other electrical infrastructure that needs to be maintained or fixed after such events, they also provide the security of being protected from severe weather and natural disasters. The main advantage of a microgrid is its higher reliability. Eventually, microgrids may be lower-cost and can take advantage of local resources. Some disadvantages are the high initial cost, complexity, technical difficulties, etc.

Before diving into the solution, it is necessary to acknowledge the simulation results of the microgrid system. By analyzing the simulation result, it can be concluded that the microgrid model is efficient enough. In reality, generation and load changes are dynamic. The system can be designed in a better way to work in a dynamic scenario. I tried to implement a perturb and observe algorithm and a machine

learning-based algorithm such as the Artificial Neural Network algorithm, but we couldn't get the desired outcome from the Artificial Neural Network. This can be implemented in the future.